

JAVASCRIPT DA O'ZGARUVCHILAR. MA'LUMOTLAR TIPI.

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Annotation. This article lists the advantages of digitalization, which is becoming a modern requirement. At the same time, in the digital education system, the teacher-student relationship reveals that it plays a very important role and influence in the educational process.

Keywords: digitization, modern education, teacher-student relations, teaching, learning, classroom management, interpersonal relationships.

Despite general digitization, teaching and learning remains an analog process today. Modern teaching research is increasingly focusing on the aspect of the teacher-student relationship. Since the quality of this relationship is one of the important factors of educational effectiveness, it needs to be constantly developed.

Digitization of education is becoming a modern requirement. This process can not only increase the achievements of students and their motivation, but also have a positive impact on the overall educational process. For example, didactic author Axel Krommer, in his article in Magazine Sprache, noted that tablets and the Internet are not just useful new tools. In his view, the real advantage of digital technologies is not that they allow old goals to be achieved quickly, but that they "open up entirely new horizons of goals". The evolving 'digital culture' infuses the whole society into a new environment for thinking, where even concepts like 'learning' and 'knowledge' take on new meanings. "

Are things and concepts that seem so appealing close to reality? Will digitalization really lead to a revolution in education? Is it true that in 10 years the educational process will change beyond recognition? No one can accurately predict future changes. We will witness this development for ourselves. In any case, current research points to completely different trends. This is exactly what proves that the anthropologically conditional similarity of teaching cannot be avoided or ignored. It should be noted that if you want to be more or less successful in this world, the meaning and significance of the "number" will only grow. "No one studies digitally," says Ralph Lanka, a media expert who has studied the issue more closely. At the same time, the potential of new tools for education is unquestionable. With their help, you can diversify tasks and individualize or personalize training. Using them can help you gain a deeper understanding of the material and create additional opportunities for reflection and collaboration.

Relying solely on technology to achieve full success in the educational process is also a very misconception. John Hetty of New Zealand in his study "Visible Education" (2009/2017) compared the average development of non-digital education (0.4) with the impact of digital education (with a few exceptions) is slightly below average. According to the researcher, the decisive role is played not by teaching aids and resources, but by the level of involvement of students in the learning process and their enthusiasm for the resources provided by the teacher in order to fully understand them. It is almost unimportant for each student to have

their own laptop (0.16), but the use of interactive instructional videos during the lesson turns out to be really useful (0.54).

Is the relationship between teacher and student an old way of teaching OR is it still in the spotlight?

John Hetty focuses on an important aspect that is often overlooked. He emphasizes: "The relationship between teacher and student is one of the strongest factors influencing student achievement." Or, as neurobiologist Joachim Bauer put it, "man is the number one motivational drug for another man. Education is first and foremost a matter of relationships."

Different opinions that arise in the student's mind - for example, whether it is better to work on difficult questions or give up ahead of time, whether I am ready to work on difficult topics, whether I can temporarily forget fatigue, whether my classmate or teammate bothers me - all this is mainly with the teacher. It depends on the relationship.

In turn, a teacher's image and openness affect his or her sense of job satisfaction. The fact that a teacher is able to communicate with different students, and that teaching brings him joy even after decades depends on whether he is a childlover by nature of the teacher, in general, can work with both children and young people, with the students of good manners and difficult upbringing, whether students are willing to work with all their strengths and weaknesses, whether they have an individual interest in them, and who can easily and confidently lead study groups on complex topics and even the most difficult situations.

Teacher-student relationship - what is it?

Although the secret of academic success and job satisfaction is hidden in the teacher-student relationship, this relationship is not given enough attention in the teacher training process. The quality of the relationship is not something that is predetermined or established only once. It is necessary to learn to develop and maintain relationships. It is important to remember that the teacher-student relationship should not be allowed to change into a personal relationship. Such a relationship should always be done within the framework of professionalism. Students need teachers as a pillar to step into new stages of life. Every student wants to be accepted, supported and managed as an individual. This is especially true when the teacher is interested in and appreciates each of their students, supports student's research, and recognizes and encourages each student's strengths and weaknesses accordingly. During the outside of the classroom process, a teacher and a student can communicate on personal topics. The teacher observes the life of the class, and most importantly, knows how to admit his mistakes, does not get angry and does not discriminate against students. All of this, of course, does not mean that he will become a "close friend" of his disciples.

Is it possible to learn it?

The skill of building interpersonal relationships cannot be learned with a set of ready-made recipes or a template. After all, it develops and refines in the process of professional activity. These relationships are very delicate and can be easily broken or destroyed. Young educators, who are just beginning their careers, often do not understand whether learners should take them seriously or keep them away from them. Experienced teachers, on the other hand, suffer from stress and professional fatigue.

The personal qualities of the teacher can also hinder the teacher-student relationship. E.g. ,

it is impossible to establish and strengthen the teacher-student relationship without demonstrating leadership qualities.

If students interrupt the teacher's opinion during the lesson, the teacher usually accepts him or her with little or no disrespect for himself and during the lesson the teacher begins to think, "This student always likes asking weird questions. I suppose, he hates me", or "This student constantly spoils the lesson with his various jokes", or, "No one appreciates that I prepared well for class." After such thoughts, the teacher's mood worsens, or students begin to feel sad and nervous, even for something trivial. In fact, perhaps the student just wanted to share his interesting thoughts on the topic and distract everyone when the students were distracted. Alfred Adler, who has been doing research in pedagogy and psychology for many years, is working on important recommendations on how to accept subjective thinking and discomfort in the above situations and direct negative energy to the beneficial side.

In conclusion, it can be said that various changes and innovations in the educational process are always evolving as a topical issue. Created twenty years ago, the tool may require modifications that do not meet modern requirements. But there is a corner in the education system, which always plays a fundamental role in the educational process. This is the teacher-student relationship. In this article, it is noted that the teacher-student relationship has not lost its importance even in the period of education, when digital technologies are the main direction, and new teachers pay more attention to student relations. We can clearly see that working on them is a requirement of the time.

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